

Figure S1. Phylogram of metazoan-associated mitovirus-like RdRp sequences.

The maximum-likelihood phylogeny was inferred from an amino-acid alignment generated with MAFFT, comprising 371 mitovirus-like RdRp sequences putatively associated with metazoan hosts. These sequences were retrieved from the "NewMitovirus UGA Codon Analysis" worksheet of Supplementary Table S3 (msystems.01002-22-s0003.xlsx) of Begeman et al. (2023). The dataset additionally includes 19 RdRp sequences from putative animal-replicating mitoviruses assigned to the proposed genus *Kvinmitovirus* (Jacquat et al., 2022; red branches), as well as four RdRp sequences tentatively assigned to the genus *Kvaramitovirus* (Jacquat et al., 2024; purple branches). Clades supported by ultrafast bootstrap values $\geq 75\%$ (UFBoot2) were collapsed to their corresponding ancestral nodes. Phylogenetic inference was performed under the LG+F+R10 substitution model with 1,000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates.